

Microwave assisted novel synthesis of isoxazole and their antibacterial activity

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Manuscript received 25 August 2008, revised 2 April 2009, accepted 3 July 2009

Abstract : 3-[3-(2-Hydroxyphenyl)-isoxazol-5-yl]-chromen-4-one (**4a-d**) have been synthesized by the action of 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-3-(4-oxo-4H-chromen-3-yl)-propane-1,3-diones and hydroxylamine hydrochloride in ethanolic medium under microwave irradiation. All the products have been evaluated for their antimicrobial activity against some Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial strains.

Keywords : Isoxazole, microwave, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Isoxazole derivatives are important as potential anti-bacterial¹, antitubercular², antiviral³, antifungal⁴ agents. Isoxazoles have been synthesized by the action of hydroxylamine hydrochloride on 1,3-dicarboxylic compounds⁵. From last few decades the use of microwave for the synthesis of organic compound has been found to be a powerful tool⁶. Therefore, in present work, we report the synthesis of isoxazoles by means of microwave irradiation.

Results and discussion

In the present work new suitably substituted 3-[3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-isoxazol-5-yl]-chromen-4-one (**4a-d**) were prepared by the action of 1,3-propanediones (**3a-d**) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride in ethanolic medium with use of microwave irradiation. 1,3-Propanediones (**3a-d**) have been synthesized by corresponding Baker-Venkataraman transformation^{7,8} of ester (**2a-d**).

Reaction between 2-hydroxy acetophenone and aromatic acid in POCl₃, pyridine afforded substituted ester (**2a-d**).

Synthesized compounds were screened for their antibacterial activity.

Experimental

The melting points were taken in an open capillary tubes. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on Nicolet 5 2DXFT

Scheme

IR spectrometer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ on Bruker ADVANCE II 400 NMR spectrometer. Domestic microwave oven of LG-680 watts has been used for reactions. The purity of synthesized compounds were checked by TLC.

Table. Yield and melting points of compounds

Compd.	R	R'	Yield (%)	M p. (°C)
2a	-CH ₃	-CH ₃	88	160
2b	-CH ₃	H	84	210
2c	H	-CH ₃	83	163
2d	H	H	79	127
3a	-CH ₃	-CH ₃	85	118
3b	-CH ₃	H	84	136
3c	H	-CH ₃	82	125
3d	H	H	79	120
4a	-CH ₃	-CH ₃	72	148
4b	-CH ₃	H	81	157
4c	H	-CH ₃	78	129
4d	H	H	70	169

Synthesis of 6-methyl-4-oxo-4H-chromen-3-carboxylic acid-2-acetyl-4-methyl-phenyl ester (2a) :

2'-Hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone (0.04 mol) and 6-methyl-4-oxo-4H-chromene-3-carboxylic acid (1a) (0.05 mol) were dissolved in dry pyridine (30 ml) in 250 ml beaker. Phosphorous oxy chloride (2.5–3.0 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring and external cooling (below 5 °C). During the addition of POCl₃, temperature was maintained below 50 °C. It was allowed to stand for 6 h and then treated with ice-cold dil. HCl to remove pyridine. The product was repeatedly washed with water and then with NaHCO₃ (10%) solution to remove organic acid and then washed with dil. NaOH (1%) to remove any untreated phenolic ketone. The product was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol, m.p. 160 °C; yield 88%, M.F. C₂₀H₁₆O₅ (Found : C, 71.22; H, 4.26. Calcd. : C, 71.39; H, 4.76); ν_{\max} 1723 (-CO-ester), 1696 (-CO- ketone), 1296 cm⁻¹ (C-O ester) etc.; δ 2.1 (6H, s, Ar-CH₃), 2.5 (3H, s, COCH₃), 7.5 (6H, m, Ar-H), 8.5 (1H, s, CH=C).

Other compounds (2b-d) were synthesized similarly.

Synthesis of 1-(2-hydroxy-5-methyl-phenyl)-3-(6-methyl-4-oxo-4H-chromen-3-yl)-propane-1,3-dione (3a) :

6-Methyl-4-oxo-4H-chromene-3-carboxylic acid-2-acetyl-4-methyl-phenyl ester (1a) (0.05 mol) was dissolved in dry pyridine (40 ml). The solution was warmed and pulverised KOH (0.15 mol) was added slowly with constant stirring. After 2 h the product was decomposed by 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid till the reaction mixture was acidic. The lemon yellow product was filtered, washed with 10% sodium bicarbonate solution to remove any hydrolysed

acid and then with water. The product was crystallized by ethanol, m.p. 118 °C; yield 85%, M.F. C₂₀H₁₆O₅ (Found : C, 71.22; H, 4.26. Calcd. : C, 71.39; H, 4.76); ν_{\max} 1715 (-C=O), 3225 (-OH), 1633 (-C=C), 1243 cm⁻¹ (Ar-O stretching in aromatic ethers); δ 2.3 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 2.5 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 7.0–7.5 (6H, m, Ar-H), 8.5 (1H, s, =C-H), 10.5 (1H, s, -OH), 12.0 (1H, s, -OH), 8.69 (2H, s, -CH₂), 1.6 (1H, bs, -OH phenolic).

Other compounds (3b-d) were synthesized in the same manner.

Synthesis of 3-[3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-isoxazol-5-yl]-chromen-4-one (4a-d) : 3-[3-(2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-phenyl)-isoxazol-5-yl]-6-methyl-chromen-4-one (3a) were synthesised by the action of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.01 mol) and 1-(2-hydroxy-5-methyl-phenyl)-3-(6-methyl-4-oxo-4H-chromen-3-yl)-propane-1,3-dione (2a) (0.01 mol) in few drops of ethanol. The reaction mixture were taken in R.B. flask capped with funnel and allowed to microwave irradiation for 2.5 min. The completion of reaction was checked by TLC. The mixture was treated with ice-cold water. Product separated out was filtered, washed and crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 148 °C; yield 72%, M.F. C₂₀H₁₅NO₄ (Found : C, 71.87; H, 3.80; N, 3.40. Calcd. : C, 71.92; H, 3.99; N, 3.80); ν_{\max} 3225.49 (-OH), 1690.03 (C=O), 1632.41 (C=N), 1618.31 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ 2.5 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 2.6 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 7.0–7.5 (6H, m, Ar-H), 8.2 (1H, s, -C=CH-), 8.5 (1H, s, =CH-O), 9.5 (1H, s, -OH).

Other compounds (4b-d) were prepared from corresponding 1,3-propanediones (3b-d) in similar manner.

Antimicrobial activity of title compounds :

The title compounds (4a-d) were screened for their antimicrobial activity against Gram-positive and Gram-negative microorganisms like *E. coli*, *A. aerogenes*, *P. vulgaris* using cup-plate method⁹. The concentration was 1 × 10⁵ CIU/ml and each well was of diameter 10 mm. The zones of inhibition were recorded after incubation for 24 h using vernier caliper.

Compounds 4a and 4b showed enhanced activity against *E. coli*, while other compound showed moderate activity. Compounds 4c and 4d showed moderate activity against *A. aerogenes*. All compounds showed good activity against *S. aureus* and *P. vulgaris*.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to SAIF/CIL, Chandigarh for providing the spectral and analytical data of the compounds.

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